

List of thirty-three unsolved arithmetic problems of the time of Ibn Khawwām

K.I.A Derouiche

DRAFT PAPER

Abstract Mathematicians have always been fascinated by the resolution of algebraic and Diophantine equations for which one seeks integer or rational solutions. We present a list of thirty-three open problems and conjectures in number theory, compiled and posed by the thirteenth-century Muslim mathematician — whose full name is ABDULLAH B. MUHAMMAD B. MUHAMMAD AL-KHAWWĀM AL-BAGHDADI, better known as d'IBN AL-KHAWWĀM — in his arithmetic treatise *al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iya fi qawā'id al-Hisābiya*. The list is presented here without commentary or solutions from our side.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Organization of the Article	2
2	Bibliographical elements concerning Ibn al-Khawwām	2
2.1	The works of Ibn al-Khawwām	3
3	The Commentators of d'AL-FAWA'ID AL-BAHA'IYA	3
4	d'Al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iya fi qawā'id al-Hisābiya	5
5	List of Ibn al-Khawwām Open Problems	5
5.1	Problems related to congruence	5
5.2	Equations of degree Four or Higher	6
5.3	Equations of degree Three	6
5.4	Equations of degree Four or Higher	7
5.5	Diophantine equations	9
5.6	Multiplicative problems	10

1 Introduction

The term open problem or unsolved problem in mathematics generally refers to problems or conjectures that have remained unproven for a long time [Kos10]. A classical example is

K.I.A Derouiche
Adgon solution, Logements 170
batiment I/04 n° 35, W112,
Mahelma, Alger, Algérie
E-mail: jkamel.derouiche@gmail.com

Poincaré conjecture, stated in 1904 in his paper *Fifth Complement to Analysis Situs*: “Is every compact, boundaryless, simply connected 3-manifold homeomorphic to the 3-sphere?” [Poi04], which was solved a century later by Grigori Perelman [Per03]. Another example is Fermat’s equation $x^n + y^n = z^n$ for $n > 3$ which was proved by Andrew Wiles [Wil95; TW95]. The Riemann Hypothesis, concerning the distribution of prime numbers, still resists every attempt at proof [Ber59; EBo22]. These conjectures are considered to belong to the category of general open problems, which cover various branches of mathematics and have been compiled into single canonical lists — for example, those announced by David Hilbert in 1900 at the International Congress of Mathematicians in Paris [Hil02]. Another well-known example is the list formulated by the mathematician Steve Smale, consisting of eighteen open problems in mathematics, which span even broader areas than those proposed by Hilbert, including theoretical computer science, mathematical economics, partial differential equations, fluid mechanics, algebraic geometry, and artificial intelligence [Sma98]. In the same spirit, but in a more restricted context, Misha Gromov formulated a list of specific open problems, mainly revolving around the fields of hyperbolic geometry, infinite groups, and metric geometry [Gro14]. Other open problems are encountered within particular subfields of mathematics, for example, the open problems of nonlinear analysis and optimization [HIR07].

In the same direction, the mathematician Jean-Louis Colliot-Thélène has proposed a list of problems in algebraic geometry and number theory, following an approach quite different from that of the general open problem lists. Colliot-Thélène formulated numerous problems, often accompanied by detailed explanations [Col22]. Within this same long-standing tradition, we present here a case in the same logic: the thirty-three problems posed by Ibn al-Khawwām. This shows that the history of open problems is not recent — it includes questions that remained unanswered for a long time — and that the list of thirty-three arithmetic problems proposed by the Muslim mathematician of the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, “*al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iyā fi qawā'id al-Hisābiya*”, is part of this tradition.

In the present article, we reproduce, without any commentary on our part, the list of thirty-three open problems in number theory as posed in the eleventh century by the mathematician Ibn al-Khawwām.

1.1 Organization of the Article

The article is organized as follows: the second section is devoted to the biography and bibliographical elements concerning Ibn al-Khawwām, followed by a section presenting the various commentators on the list of thirty-three problems Ibn al-Khawwām. The fourth section discusses and sets out the thirty-three arithmetic problems.

2 Bibliographical elements concerning Ibn al-Khawwām

Abdallah ibn Muhammad ibn Abd al-Razzāq Al-kharabāwi Imaā El-Edine Ibn al-Khawwām born in 643H/1245 in Baghdad, was a physician, writer, philosopher, and mathematician. He was nicknamed “the Arithmetician” in Baghdad by his peers, due to his fame and his influence on the arithmetic of his era, which he maintained throughout his life, as reported by the historian Shams ad-Din adh-Dhahabi [Abu16].

He was well-versed in the religious sciences, as was customary at the time.¹

Because of his fame, Ibn al-Khawwām was widely sought after at court as a tutor for the sons of ministers and princes in Isfahan, under the reign of Abaka Khan (d. 680H/1282), son of Hülagü Khan. Around 475H/1277, at the age of thirty-two, in this same city, Ibn al-Khawwām wrote his book *al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iyā fi qawā'id al-Hisābiya* during the month of Sha'bān (January 675H/1276) [Faz95].

He taught Shafi'ite jurisprudence (fiqh) at Dar ad-Dhahab in Baghdad, directed the Mashyakhāt ar-Riba of Baghdad, and remained active there until his death in 724H/1324. Among his students was the eminent mathematician and physicist Kamāl al-Dān al-Fārisī (1267–1319) [Al-96].

2.1 The works of Ibn al-Khawwām

The historians Shams ad-Dīn adh-Dhahabi and Ibn Hajar al-'Asqalāni mention only four works ([Abu16], [Asq72]) attributed to Ibn al-Khawwām:

1. An Introduction to Medicine.
2. *AL-Tadkira Al-Saādiya Fi EL-KAWANIN AL-TYBIYA*. This is a manuscript dealing with medicine, catalogued in the al-Awqāf library in Mosul. However, no other author has mentioned this work. We believe that this book could possibly be a version of his Introduction to Medicine; however, in our opinion, it does not appear to be the same work.
3. *Rissaālat Fi Al-Firassaā*(Epistle on Physiognomy).
4. *Risāla fi fām al-Maqāla al-Ashirā min Kitāb Uqlūdis*.
5. *Al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iyā fi qawā'id al-Hisābiya* (Our present book).

3 The Commentators of d'AL-FAWA'ID AL-BAHA'IYA

Ibn Khawwām's book has attracted considerable interest from its appearance until today. Several commentators have addressed the fifth and final volume, which is devoted to the list of thirty-three problems some have treated only certain parts of it, others have commented mainly on questions of an algebraic nature, while yet others have merely suggested possible approaches. Another category of commentators reproduced the solutions that were provided and offered explanations, often with a pedagogical purpose. To the best of our knowledge, no commentator has actually solved the problems posed in this list, with the exception of the nearly complete work of Abdeljouad and Hemida [MH86], prior to the modern resolution.

- Ibn al-Khawwām Kamāl ad-Dīn Hassan al-Fārisī(12 January 1267- 730H/1319), in his work entitled "Assās al-qawā'id fi usul al-fawā'id" (The Foundation of Rules in the Principles of Applications) [DD06], presents an introduction and five chapters dealing with arithmetic rules, notarial and commercial transactions, the measurement of areas and volumes, and the last two treatises focus on algebra.
- Abd Ali ibn Muhammad ibn Husayn Birjandi[Kus14], the date of his death is not precisely known and deserves further clarification. Hajji Khalifa mentions three different

¹ At that time, and even long before, education was conducted in higher colleges (madrasas) where both religious subjects and secular disciplines (literature, grammar, astronomy, mathematics) were taught. These colleges hosted professors and students for teaching activities on a wide variety of topics [DM12].

- dates for Ibn al-Khawwām's death in three separate places, around 934H/1528. Al-Birjandi wrote marginal commentaries on al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iyā. Tihirānī notes this reference to Hajji Khalifa ([M M09], [Kha41]).
- Ibn al-Khawwām himself hints, at the end of the fourth book of al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iyā, that he may have written his own commentary on this treatise elsewhere, but this commentary has not reached us [MH86].
 - Yahya Ahmad al-Kāshānī [Kās20] (d.744H/1344) commented on Ibn al-Khawwām's book in *Id al-Maqid f Fawā'id al-Fawā'id*. Abdeljouad & Al also pointed out the frequent confusion between Yaḥyā Imāad al-Kāshī and Jamshīd al-Kāshī, who lived at the end of the fourteenth and beginning of the fifteenth century [MH86] and is famous in the Western world for the theorem that bears his name in trigonometry: $c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab \cos \theta$
 - Both Yahya Ahmad al-Kāshī and Jamshīd al-Kāshī published books on arithmetic with very similar titles. The book by Yahya Ahmad al-Kāshī is entitled *Kitāb al-Hisab* (Book of Arithmetic), whereas that of Jamshīd al-Kāshī is entitled "Talkhis Miftah Fi 'Ilam al Hisāb" (Summary of the Key in the Science of Arithmetic). The latter seems to be the work dealing with Ibn al-Khawwām problems, and we have obtained a manuscript copy of it.
 - The mathematician Turk Ramāadān - the historian Öğr Üyesi Hüseyin ALi notes that he was still alive in 1092H/1681, after having completed his work *Solution of the Sketch for the Governors in the Explanation of the Sketch of Beha-eddin Amili* [El-81a; El-81b]. No information is given about his date of birth or death [ALİ19]. This book has not yet been edited and remains available only in manuscript form.
 - Abud El-Rahim Ibn Abu Bākar Ibn Soulymān El Māarachiī (1068H/1658) with the title of his manuscript: *Rissala al-Bahā'iyā Fi Al-Hissab* [Māa84] [Kah57].
 - The Kurdish mathematician Omar ibn Aāmad al-M El Djali El kurdi [El-], author of the book entitled *Commentaries on Problematic Places and Annotations on Symbols Resulting from Problematic Investigations*.
 - The mathematician al-Amiliī (953H/1547-1031H/1622) reproduced extracts from al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iyā; his seven unsolved problems appear among the thirty-three open problems of Ibn al-Khawwām (specifically problems 4, 8, 17, 18, 19, 24, and 32) [Ami81].
 - Mahdi Abdeljaouad and Hmida Hedfi commented on Ibn al-Khawwām treatise in their article *Vers une étude des aspects historiques et mathématiques des problèmes ouverts d'Ibn al-Khawwām (XIIIe s.)* [MH86]. Despite its 23 pages, their work remains to this day the most comprehensive attempt compared with earlier efforts by other mathematicians. They review multiple solutions, relying on the work of other scholars who had already treated some of these problems, while also identifying problems that had not been mentioned and that do not require sophisticated methods problems that today can be considered elementary. Some of these problems are even connected with questions that were later known as Fermat Last Theorem (solved by Wiles [Wil95]), which can now be approached with elementary methods and whose demonstrations they partially reconstruct.
 - The French mathematician Marre translated al-Amili book *Khélasat al Hisāb* (Essence of Calculation) into French, and on this occasion reproduced problems 4, 8, 17, 18, 19, 24, and 32 from al-Fawā'id al-Bahā'iyā as included in al-Amili book [Mar46]. This was preceded by a German translation of *Khélasat al Hisāb* by the German mathematician Nesselmann [Alh43].
 - The historian of science Moustafa Mawaldi devoted the third volume of his dissertation to the mathematician ḩasan al-Fārisī [Maw89], as well as to the thirty-three problems of Ibn al-Khawwām, treating them in great detail. Professor Mahdi Abdeljaouad kindly

provided me with a copy of this doctoral dissertation dedicated to Ibn al-Khawwām list [DA23].

- The Turkish historian ihsan Fazlioglu [Faz95] has also worked on the thirty-three problems, contributing solutions inspired by the work of Mahdi Abdeljaouad and Hmida Hedfi, and adding new insights, including a discussion of Fermat conjecture.
- The mathematician and historian of mathematics Ahmed Djebbar, drawing on the article by Mahdi Abdeljaouad and Hmida Hedfi [MH86], reproduces in the appendix of his work Une histoire scientifique des pays d’islam : entretiens avec Jean Rosmorduc [AJ01] the list of the thirty-three problems of Ibn al-Khawwām, without adding commentary of his own [DA22].

4 d’Al-Fawā’id al-Bahā’iya fi qawā’id al-Hisābiya

Abdeljaouad mentions five books that make up Ibn al-Khawwām treatise al-Fawā’id al-Bahā’iya fi qawā’id al-isā’biya [MH86]:

Book 1: On multiplication, fractions, division, and root extraction.

Book 2 : On commercial transactions and their laws.

Book 3 : On areas and volumes.

Book 4 : On algebra (al-jabr wal-muqbalā).

Book 5 : 5: On the resolution of algebraic problems.

it is this fifth book of al-Fawā’id al-Bahā’iya fi qawā’id al-isābiya, devoted to the resolution of algebraic problems, that will be the subject of the present section.

5 List of Ibn al-Khawwām Open Problems

5.1 Problems related to congruence

Remark 1 Problems 17 and 19 were posed by al-’Āmilī. [MH86]

Problem 1 Find two square numbers such that both their sum and their difference are also squares.

Modern formulation: $x^2 + y^2 = 0$ et $x^2 - y^2 = 0$

Problem 18 Find a number that admits a square root such that, if you add ten dirhams to it, the result admits a square root, and if you subtract ten dirhams, the result also admits a square root.

Modern formulation: $x^2 + 10 = 0$ et $x^2 - 10 = 0$

Problem 19 A square that admits a root: if you add its root and two dirhams to it, the result is a square; if you subtract its root and two dirhams, it is again a square.

Modern formulation: $x^2 + (x + 2) = 0$ et $x^2 - (x + 2) = 0$

5.2 Equations of degree Four or Higher

Problem 16. Find a square number such that, if ten times its square root and ten dirhams are subtracted from it, the result is still a perfect square.

Modern formulation: $(10x + 10) - x^2 = 0$.

Problem 26. Divide a given number into two parts, one being a cube and the other a square.

Modern formulation: $x^3 + y^2 = n$, given n

Problem 27. Divide a given number into two cubic numbers.

Modern formulation: $x^3 + y^3 = n$, given n

5.3 Equations of degree Three

Problems 15, 21, 22, 25, 28, 29, 32, and 33 fall into the category of univariate polynomial equations of degree four or higher. These can be transformed into Diophantine equations or treated via Galois theory, provided that the Galois group is solvable — which we shall do whenever possible.

Problem 15. Divide ten into two numbers such that, if the smaller is divided by the larger, the result is added to the latter, and the whole is multiplied by the smaller, one obtains a given number.

Modern formulation: $x + y = 10$; $y \left(\frac{y}{x} + x \right) = n$, $x > y$, given n .

Problem 21. Find a square number such that, when its root is subtracted from it and the remainder is multiplied by its root, the result is the original square..

Modern formulation: $(x^2 - x) \sqrt{x^2 - x} = x^2$.

$$\left((x^2 - x) \sqrt{x^2 - x} \right)^2 = (x^2)^2 \quad (1)$$

After simplification, we obtain the equation $x^6 - 3x^5 + 2x^4 - x^3$, Abdeljouad [MH86] Proceeds by a change of variable by setting $X = x - 1$ solves this equation by considering x as real, and shows the impossibility of finding rational solutions.

Problem 22. Find two numbers whose difference is ten times the root of the smaller, and such that if each is divided by the other and the results are added, the sum is equal to the root of the smaller number.

Modern formulation: $x - y = 10\sqrt{y}$; $\frac{x}{y} + \frac{y}{x} = \sqrt{y}$.

Problem 25. Divide a given number into two parts such that, if the number is divided by each part and by their difference, the sum of all the quotients is a given number.

Modern formulation: $x + y = a$; $\frac{a}{x} + \frac{a}{y} + \frac{a}{x-y} = b$; $x > y$.

Problem 28. A square from which its third and its root are subtracted; ten times the root of the result is equal to one third of the square plus its root.

Modern formulation: $10\sqrt{x^2 - (\frac{x^2}{3} + x)} = \frac{x^2}{3} + x.$

Resolution. This problem can be reduced by squaring both sides. By squaring both terms, the problem reduces to a quartic equation. This quartic can be solved by radicals using Ferrari's method, yielding the (complex) solutions. Abdeljaouad further reduces the problem to a cubic equation of the form

$$X^3 - 603X + 2098 = 0$$

obtained by the change of variable $X = x + 2$ [MH86]. This cubic can be solved using Cardano's method. In both Ferrari's and Cardano's approaches, the discriminant is negative, implying that all solutions are complex. Therefore, the equation admits no rational solutions.

Problem 29. Find the number of garments whose total price is a given number of dirhams, knowing that the price of a single garment plus the square root of the number of garments is equal to a given number.

Modern formulation: $xy = a; x + \sqrt{y} = b,$ given a and $b.$

Problem 32. Divide ten into two numbers such that, when each is divided by the other and the quotients are added together, the result is equal to one of the two numbers.

Modern formulation: $x + y = 10; \frac{x}{y} + \frac{y}{x} = x.$

Problem 33. Divide ten into two numbers such that, if the larger is divided by the smaller and the quotient is multiplied by the larger, and the smaller is divided by the larger and the quotient is multiplied by the smaller, then the difference between the larger result and the smaller result is a fixed number.

Modern formulation: $x + y = 10; x\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) - y\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) = n,$ given $n.$

5.4 Equations of degree Four or Higher

Problems 3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 17, and 20 are classified as belonging to the category of single-variable polynomial equations of degree 4 or higher, which can be transformed into Diophantine equations or studied through Galois theory if the equation's group is solvable—something we will do when possible and mention whenever the occasion allows.

Probleme 4. Divide ten into two numbers such that, if you add the square root to each number and multiply the resulting sums together, you obtain a given number.

Modern formulation: $x + y = 10; (x + \sqrt{x})(y + \sqrt{y}) = n,$ given $n.$

Resolution. It is a matter of finding the appropriate change of variables by setting $X^2 = x$ and $Y^2 = y$, which transforms the problem into a system. (2)

$$\sigma(s, i) = \begin{cases} X^2 + Y^2 = 10 \\ (X^2 + X)(Y^2 + Y) = n \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

After some algebraic manipulations between the two equations, $Y^2 = 10 - X^2$, as we expand in the equation: $(X^2 + X)(10 - X^2 + \sqrt{10 - X^2}) = n$

$$(X^2 + X)\sqrt{10 - X^2} = n - (X^2 + X)10 + (X^2 + X)X^2$$

Probleme 5. Divide ten into two numbers such that, if each is divided by the other, the resulting quotients are added together, the sum is squared, and then multiplied by one of the two numbers, the result is a given number.

Modern formulation: $x + y = 10$; $\left(\frac{x}{y} + \frac{y}{x}\right)^2 x = n$, given n , we expand the expression $\left(\frac{x}{y} + \frac{y}{x}\right)^2 x = n$, By simplifying,

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{x^2 + y^2}{yx}\right)^2 x &= n \\ x^4 + 2x^2y^2 + y^4 &= ny^2x \end{aligned}$$

we substitute y par $10 - x$ in the equation, we obtain

$$x^4 + 2x^2(10 - x)^2 + (10 - x)^4 = n(10 - x)^2x$$

Problem 6. Divide ten into two numbers such that, if each is multiplied by its square root and the results are added together, the sum is a given number.

Modern formulation: $x + y = 10$; $x\sqrt{x} + y\sqrt{y} = n$, given n .

Resolution. The problem can be written as the following system:

$$\sigma(s, i) = \begin{cases} x + y = 10 \\ x\sqrt{x} + y\sqrt{y} = n \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

A change of variables, proposed by Abdeljaouad, consists in setting $X^2 = x$ and $Y^2 = y$; Under this substitution, the system (3) becomes $X^3 + Y^3 = n$ and $X^2 + Y^2 = 10$. Thus, the problem reduces to decomposing a given number n as a sum of two cubes $X^3 + Y^3 = n$. It then suffices to perform algebraic manipulations to determine the admissible solutions $Y^2 = 10 - X^2$ for the value Y of the equation $X^3 + Y^3 = n$, we need to expand

$$X^3 + (10 - X^2)^3 = n$$

the equation obtained is

$$X^6 - 2X^3n + X^2 + n^2 - 10 \quad (4)$$

Our goal is to find rational solutions of 4; the question is how to solve it?.

Problem 11. Find two squares whose sum is ten, and such that if you add the square root to each, the results are also perfect squares.

Modern formulation: $x^2 + y^2 + 10, x + \sqrt{x} = 0; y + \sqrt{y} = 0$.

Problem 17. A person receives an inheritance of 10 dirhams decreased by the square root of the inheritance of a second person. The inheritance of the latter is equal to 5 dirhams decreased by the square root of the inheritance of the first person.

Modern formulation: $y = 10 - \sqrt{y}; x = 5 - \sqrt{y}$.

Resolution. By applying the same change of variables as in problems *Num*, or proceeding differently if necessary, we set, $x - 5 = \sqrt{(5)}$ and $y = 10 - \sqrt{(10)}$, By substitution, we obtain:

$$(x - 5)^2 = (10 - \sqrt{(x)})$$

$$(x - 5)^2$$

Problem 20. Find a square number which, when multiplied by itself and increased by ten times its square root and ten dirhams, becomes a number that has a square root.

Modern formulation: $(x^2)^2 + 10x + 10 = 0$.

5.5 Diophantine equations

A very interesting book in which recent solutions are recorded[Guy04]

Problem 2. Find three square numbers whose sum is a square, such that the sum of the squares of any two of them is equal to the square of the third.

Modern formulation: $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 0; (x^2)^2 + (y^2)^2 = (z^2)^2; (x^2)^2 + (y^2)^2 = (z^2)^2; (y^2)^2 + (z^2)^2 = (x^2)^2$.

Problem 3. Find a right triangle whose sides are perfect squares.

Modern formulation: $(x^2)^2 + (y^2)^2 = (z^2)^2$.

Problem 8. Find three proportional square numbers whose sum is also a square.

Modern formulation: $\frac{x^2}{y^2} = \frac{y^2}{z^2}; x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 0$.

Problem 9. Find two squares such that the product of one of them by their sum is equal to the square of the other.

Modern formulation: $(x^2 + y^2) x^2 = (y^2)^2$.

Problem 12. Find a cube such that, when one dirham is added to it, the result is another perfect cube.

Modern formulation : $x^3 + 1 = 0$ et $x^3 + y^3 = 0$

Problem 13 Find two cubes such that, if each is divided by the other and the results are added together, the sum is a perfect square.

Modern formulation: $\frac{x^3}{y^3} + \frac{y^3}{x^3} = 0 = a^2$.

Problem 14. Find a square number such that, if each is divided by the other, the results are added together and multiplied by one of them, the outcome is a perfect square.

Modern formulation: $x^2 \left(\frac{x^2}{y^2} + \frac{y^2}{x^2} \right) = 0$.

Problem 20 Find a square number which, when multiplied by itself and increased by ten times its square root and ten dirhams, becomes a number that has a square root.

Modern formulation: $(x^2)^2 + 10x + 10$

Problem 23. Find a cube whose difference from its square is a perfect square.

Modern formulation $(x^3) - (x^3)^2 = 0$ et $(x^3)^2 - x^3 = 0$

5.6 Multiplicative problems

Problem 10 Find four square numbers such that if the first is multiplied by itself, then by the second, then by the third, and the total by the fourth, the result yields the four numbers again.

Modern formulation: $(x^2 x^2; x^2 x^2 y^2; x^2 x^2 y^2 z^2; x^2 x^2 y^2 z^2 t^2) = (x^2; y^2; z^2; t^2)$.

Problem 30 Find three cubic numbers such that if the first is multiplied by the second, and the result by the third, the final product is a given number.

Modern formulation: $x^3 y^3 z^3 = a$; given a .

Problem 31 An employee, whose monthly salary is a fixed but unknown number of dirhams, worked during a month for a number of days equal to the square root of the salary and received a predetermined amount of money.

Modern formulation: $\frac{x}{30} \sqrt{x} = a$; given a .

Acknowledgement

We thank Djebarr Ahmed and Mahdi Abdeljouad for his discussions and helpful, constructive advice, which led to a significant improvement of the paper.

References

- [Kās20] Y. I. A. Kāshānī. *Īdāh al-maqāṣid li-farāid al-fawāid*. Arabic. Pennsylvania, USA: University of Pennsylvania Libraries, 1320, p. 353.
- [El-81a] T.I.H El-Djazri. *Solution de l'esquisse pour les gouvernement dans l'explication l'esquisse de Beha-eddin Amili*. Arabic. Manuscript 6346. King Saud University, KSA: Makhtota of King Saud University, 1681. 81 pp. Arithmetic.
- [El-81b] T.I.H El-Djazri. *Solution de l'esquisse pour les gouvernement dans l'explication l'esquisse de Beha-eddin Amili*. Arabic. Manuscript 7934. Istanbul, Turkey: institution, 1681, pp. 111–60.
- [Māa84] A.E.I.B.I.S Māarachiī. *Chaarah Rissala al-Bahā'iya Fi Al-Hissab*. Arabic. Manuscript 1020. Douha, Qatar: Qatar National Library, 1684. 21 pp. Qatar Digital Library.
- [Alh43] Mohammed Beha-eddin ben Alhossain aus Amul. *LIBRARY OF WELLESLEY COLLEGE. PURCHASED FROM LIBRARY FUNDS. Essenz der Rechenkunst. arabisch und deutsch*. Akademiensclie Buchtruckerri. Germany. Trans. by G. H. F Nesselmann. Berlin, Germany: Bei G. Reimer, 1843. 164 pp.
- [Mar46] Astride Marre. *Nouvelles annales de mathématiques. Journal des Candidats aux Écoles Polytechnique Et Normale (Classic Reprint)*. Vol. 5: *Khélasat al Hisáb ou essence du calcul de Behā-eddin Mohammed ben al-Hosain al-Aamouli*. French. Ed. by Terquem. 1. Forgotten Books, 1846, pp. 263–323. 732 pp. DOI: [978-0260779489](https://doi.org/10.2607779489).
- [Ber59] Riemann Bernhard. *Ueber die Anzahl der Primzahlen unter einer gegebenen Grösse. Gesammelte Werke*. Deutsch. Monatsber. Teubner, Leipzig: Akad Berlin, 1859, pp. 136–145.
- [Hil02] David Hilbert. *LES GRANDS CLASSIQUES GAUTHIER-VILLARS*. Vol. 1: *Sur les problèmes futurs des mathématiques : les 23 problèmes*. French. Trans. by Léonce Laugel. JACQUES GABAY. Paris, France: GAUTHIER-VILLARS, 1902, p. 57.
- [Poi04] Henri Poincaré. “Cinquième complément à l'Analysis situs”. In: *Rendiconti del Circolo Matematico di Palermo* 15 (Dec. 1904), pp. 45–110. DOI: [10.1007/BF03014091](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03014091). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03014091>.
- [Kha41] Hajji Khalifa. “Kashf az-Zunun 'an asami al-Kutub wa z-funun”. Arabic. In: vol. 2. 2 vols. Beyrouth, Lebanon: DAR IHYA EL-TOURATH AL-ARABI, 1941.
- [Kah57] Omar Reda Kahaala. *Le dictionnaire des auteurs, les traductions des livres arabes, les traductions*. Arabic. In: *booktitle*. Ed. by editor. Vol. 5. Beyrouth, Liban: Bibliotheque Mouthana- Daar Ihiya Touraht Arabi, 1957, p. 4901.
- [Asq72] Asqalāni. *Ad-durar al Kamina fi ayan al mi'a al-thāmina*. Arab. Ed. by Encyclopaedia of Ottoman. With a comment. by Al-Muiyyad Thaān. Muhammed Abed. 2nd ed. Vol. 3. 4 vols. 2. Hyderabad(Inde): Encyclopaedia of Ottoman, 1972, pp. 76–77. 2039 pp.
- [Ami81] Baha'ad-Din Amili. *Mathematical Works Baha' ad-Din al-Amili*. Arabic. Ed. by Dar Al-Chourouk. Trans. Arabic and comm. by Shawki Djallal. With annots. by Shawki Djallal. 1st ed. Egypt, Cairo, 1981. 227 pp.
- [MH86] Abdeljouad Mahdi and Hedfi Hmida. “Vers Une Etude des Aspects Historiques Et Mathématiques des Problèmes Ouverts D'Ibn Al-Khawwam (XIII S)”. French. In: *Histoire des Mathématiques Arabes*. Premier Colloque International d'Alger sur l'Histoire des Mathématiques Arabes (Alger, Dec. 3, 1986). Ed. by ENS Kouba. ENS Kouba. Algeria: ENS Kouba, Dec. 1986, pp. 159–178.

- [Maw89] Moustafa Mawaldi. *L'algèbre de Kamal al-Din al-Farisi :édition critique et étude historique. Les problèmes impossibles*. French. 3 vols. 3. Paris, France: Université de la Sorbonne Nouvelle, 1989. 23 pp.
- [Faz95] İhsan Fazlioglu. “İbn El-Havvam, Eserleri ve El-Fevadid El-Bahaiyye Fi El-Kavaid El-Hisabiyye'deki Çözüksüz Problemler Bahsi (Ibn Al-Hawwam (D.724/1324), His Works and The Section on Insoluble Problems in Al-Fawa'id Al-Bahaiyya Fi Al-Qawaid Al-Hisabiyya)”. Turc. In: *Osmanlı Bilimi Araştırmaları (Ottoman Science Research). Studies in Ottoman Science* 1, 2458-7982 (Dec. 1995). Ed. by Kaan Ata, pp. 69–128. ISSN: 1303-3123. Istanbul, Turkey.
- [TW95] Richard Taylor and Andrew Wiles. “Ring-theoretic properties of certain Hecke algebras”. In: *journaltitle* 141 (3 1995), pp. 553–572. DOI: [10.2307/2118560](https://doi.org/10.2307/2118560). URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2118560>.
- [Wil95] Andrew Wiles. “Modular elliptic curves and Fermat’s Last Theorem”. English. In: *Annals of Mathematics* 141.3 (May 1995). Ed. by Princeton University and the Institute for Advanced Study, pp. 443–551. DOI: [10.2307/2118559](https://doi.org/10.2307/2118559). Mathematics Department, Princeton University.
- [Al-96] Abd El-Razek Ibn Ahmed Ibn El-Fuwṭī Al-Chāyībāi. “Madjmaā AL-Adaāb 'Fi Moudjām El-Alkāab”. Arabic. In: •. Ed. and comm. by M. Kādīmm. 1st ed. Vol. 2. 6 vols. Tehran, Iran: Société d'impression et d'édition, Ministère de la Culture et de l'orientation islamique, 1996, p. 591.
- [Sma98] S Smale. “Mathematical problems for the next century”. English. In: *The Mathematical Intelligencer* 20 (2 Mar. 1998), pp. 7–15. ISSN: 0343-6993. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03025291>. 12 January 2009.
- [AJ01] Djebbar. Ahmed and Rosmorduc. Jean. *Une histoire scientifique des pays d'islam : entretiens avec Jean Rosmorduc*. Français. Ed. by Seuil. With annots. by Jean Rosmorduc. 1st ed. 2001-05-16. Paris: Points, 2001, p. 2. 384 pp. ISBN: 2020395495.
- [Per03] Grisha Perelman. “The entropy formula for the Ricci flow and its geometric applications”. English. In: *ArXiv e-prints* (Nov. 2003), p. 39. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.math/0211159](https://arxiv.org/abs/math/0211159). eprint: [arXiv:math/0211159](https://arxiv.org/abs/math/0211159) (math**). URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/math/0211159> (visited on 11/11/2002).
- [Guy04] Richard K. Guy. *Unsolved Problems in Number Theory*. Unsolved Problems in Intuitive Mathematics. Ed. by K.A. Bencsath. Ed. by P.R. Halmos. 3 vols. Problem Books in Mathematics 3. New York, USA: Springer New York, NY, 2004. 455 pp. ISBN: 978-1-4419-1928-1. DOI: [10.1007/978-0-387-26677-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-26677-0). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-3585-4>. eBook: 978-0-387-26677-0.
- [DD06] Ahmed Djebarr and SAVOIE Denis. “Kamal ad-Din al-Farisi, physicien et mathématicien novateur”. French. In: *Sous le ciel de Perse* 334 (Jan. 1, 2006). Ed. by Sous le ciel de Perse. Paris, p. 19. ISSN: 16210085. Paris: Palais de la découverte.
- [HIR07] J.-B. HIRIART-URRUTY. “Potpourri of Conjectures and Open Questions in Nonlinear Analysis and Optimization”. English. In: *SIAM Review* 49 (2 Apr. 2007). Ed. by SIAM Review, pp. 255–273. ISSN: 0036-1445. DOI: [10.1137/050633500](https://doi.org/10.1137/050633500). eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1137/050633500>.
- [M M09] Tihriānī M. M. A. B. “Tabaghat Aa'lam Al-Shia”. Arabic. In: 1st ed. 17 vols. Beyrouth, Lebanon: DAR EHIA AL-TOURATH AL-ARABI, 2009.
- [Kos10] G Kosyvas. “PROBLÈMES OUVERTS : NOTION, CATÉGORIES ET DIFFICULTÉS”. Fr. In: *ANNALES de DIDACTIQUE et de SCIENCES COGNITIVES. Revue internationale de didactique des mathématiques* 15 (2 Apr. 2010). Ed. by IREM de Strasbourg, pp. 45–73. ISSN: 0987-7576.

- [DM12] Ahmed Djebarr and Marc Moyon. *Les Sciences Arabes En Afrique. Mathématiques et Astronomie IX-XIX siècles*. Suivi de Nubdha fi’ilm al hisab, d’Ahmad Babir al-Arawani. French. Ed. by Apic Edition. Ed. by Editions Grandvaux. 1. Ben Aknoun, Alger, 2012. Chap. 1. 191 pp. ISBN: 978-9961-769-85-0.
- [Gro14] Misha Gromov. *Number of Questions*. English. Miscellaneous mathematics. Institut des Hautes Études Scientifiques. Oct. 3, 2014. URL: <https://www.ihes.fr/~gromov/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/problems-sept2014-copy.pdf>.
- [Kus14] T. Kusuba. “Birjandi: Abd Alı ibn Muḥammad Ibn Husayn Al-Birjandi”. English. In: *Biographical Encyclopedia of Astronomers*. Ed. by Thomas Hockey. Ed. by V. Trimble. 2nd ed. 26-12-2016. New York, NY: Springer New York, 2014, pp. 225–226. ISBN: 978-1-4419-9917-7. DOI: [10.1007/978-1-4419-9917-7_158](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9917-7_158).
- [Abu16] Shams al-Din Abu ’Abdallah Ibn al-Dhahabi. *Siyar a’lam al-nubala (The Lives of Noble Figure)*. Arab. Ed. by Mu’assassat al-Risalah. With a comment. by Arna’ut Shuaib Al and Marouf Bashshar Awwad. Mu’assassat al-Risalah. 29 vols. Beirut(Lebanon), 2016. 18388 pp.
- [ALİ19] Öğr. Üyesi Hüseyin ALİ. “CİZRE ÂLİMLERİNİN BİYOGRAFİK BİLGİLERİ”. Arabic. In: *The Journal of Agri Islamic Sciences. Dergi Park AKADEMIK*, 2619-9327 (5 Dec. 2019), pp. 1–10. ISSN: 2619-9327. URL: <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/885967> (visited on 12/15/2019).
- [EBo22] E.Bombieri. *Problems of the Millennium: the Riemann Hypothesis. Official Problem Description*. English. Institute for Advanced Study. June 20, 2022. URL: http://www.claymath.org/sites/default/files/official_problem_description.pdf (visited on 06/20/2022).
- [Col22] Jean-Louis Colliot-Thélène. *Une liste de problèmes*. English. In: *Mathematics Going Forward. Collected Mathematical Brushstrokes*. Ed. by Jean-Michel Morel and Bernard Teissier. .Lecture Notes in Mathematics. Lecture Notes in Mathematics 1. Berlin, Germany: Springer Cham, 2022. Chap. Algebraic Geometry, pp. 7–28. ISBN: 978-3-031-12243-9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-12244-6>.
- [DA22] K.I.A Derouiche and Djebarr Ahmed. *Private communication by e-mail*. French. Apr. 15, 2022.
- [DA23] K.I.A Derouiche and Mahdi Abdeljouad. “Private communication by e-mail”. French. Private e-mail. 2023.
- [El-] O.I.A.M.D El-Kurdi. *Commentaires sur les lieux problématiques et les notifications sur des symboles issues de recherches problématiques*. Arabic. Manuscript 1363. 63 pp.